

Idleness, Illiteracy, and Banditry: Unemployment as a Catalyst for Crime in Northwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

This article explores the relationship between idleness, illiteracy, and rising banditry in Northwestern Nigeria. The study argues that the growing prevalence of unemployment and illiteracy, particularly among youth, are significant contributing factors to the increase in criminal activities, including banditry, cattle rustling, and other crimes. Through a mixed-methods approach, the research incorporates a comprehensive literature review and qualitative interviews with key informants, including community leaders, educators, victims, and youth. Findings indicate that a lack of employment opportunities and inadequate educational infrastructure, particularly among pastoralists, out-of-school children, and the 'mabarata' (beggars), perpetuate cycles of poverty and crime. The study emphasizes the urgent need for job creation initiatives and skill development programs to mitigate the factors driving banditry. The article posits that Northwestern Nigeria can take significant steps toward reducing banditry and enhancing community security by addressing unemployment and illiteracy as well as providing viable alternatives for the youth.

Keywords: Banditry, Crime, Idleness, Illiteracy, Unemployment.

1.0 Introduction

In recent years, Northwestern Nigeria has faced an alarming rise in banditry and criminal activities. These issues have become increasingly pronounced in the region which is predominantly inhabited by the Hausa people, where traditional structures of community and livelihood are being undermined. Banditry (characterized by armed robbery, kidnapping for ransom, and other violent crimes) has created a state of insecurity and significantly disrupted local economies and livelihoods. In recent years it distrubs farming and other commercial activities especially in villages under Zamfara, Katsina, and Sokoto states.¹

There are several factors contributing to this surge in criminal activities, but central ones are joblessness and illiteracy among the youth. High unemployment rates, particularly in Northwestern Nigeria, have left many young people without purpose or direction, leading them to seek alternative, which sometimes involve criminal means of survival. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2023), "Unemployment rates in Northern Nigeria are among the highest in the country." That left many youths with the feeling of being marginalized and disillusioned about their future prospects.

Furthermore, the combination of poverty, lack of education, and social exclusion creates a fertile ground for recruitment into criminal networks. The alarming increase in the number of out-of-school children, especially among the *mabarata* population, exacerbates the problem. These children, often lacking basic education and vocational skills, become increasingly vulnerable to exploitation by bandits and terrorist groups, along side other minor criminal activities. Pastoralism and the *bara* (begging) have perpetuated cycles of poverty and idleness Northwestern Nigeria's youth.

¹ See Sarkin Gulbi *et al* (2024a).

This study explores idleness and illiteracy to ascertain how they relate to banditry and other crimes in Northwestern Nigeria. It emphasizes the importance of providing basic literacy and meaningful employment opportunities, which are essential for the socioeconomic development of the region and for fostering social stability. The focus will be on new job opportunities that require skills, such as language services and technology services, which can be effectively leveraged to empower the youth and reduce crime.

1.1 Methodology

This study employs a mixed-methods approach to explore the relationship between idleness, illiteracy, and crimes (especially banditry) in Northwestern Nigeria. A comprehensive literature review was conducted to gather existing knowledge on the socioeconomic conditions of the region, particularly focusing on the *bara* system and the challenges faced by *makiyaya* (Fulani pastoralist). Key sources included academic articles, government reports, and publications from organizations such as the *International Crisis Group* and the *National Bureau of Statistics*.

Qualitative methods included semi-structured interviews with key informants, such as community members, educators, and victims from affected communities. These interviews explored personal narratives and contextual factors contributing to the cycle of idleness, illiteracy, and crime. Focus group discussions were also held with youth from diverse backgrounds, including *mabarata* and some Fulani pastoralist (usually residing within outskirts of towns), to understand their perspectives on joblessness, illiteracy, and the motivations behind engaging in criminal activities.

The qualitative data from interviews and focus groups were transcribed and thematically analyzed to identify recurring themes related to the connection between idleness and banditry. Ethical approval was secured prior to data collection, ensuring that participants were informed about the study's objectives and their rights, including the right to withdraw from participation at any time. Informed consent was obtained verbally, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the research process. The study acknowledges certain limitations, including potential biases in self-reported data and difficulties in accessing some communities and especially some individuals (key actors) due to security concerns.

2.1 The Link Between Idleness and Criminal Activities

The relationship between idleness and criminal activities is complex, as demonstrated by various studies in criminology and sociology.² Economic deprivation, unemployment, and unstructured time often leave individuals, particularly youth, vulnerable to criminal behavior. Aiyede and Adetola (2022 p. 73) highlight that “idle youth are often more vulnerable to recruitment by criminal groups, as they seek alternatives to their economic woes.” In regions such as Northwestern Nigeria, where job opportunities are scarce (especially due to high level of illiteracy), youth idleness is a critical factor in the rise of criminal activities, including banditry and cattle rustling.

Strain theory, introduced by Robert Merton, explains how individuals under economic and social pressures may resort to crime when legitimate opportunities are inaccessible. Mohammed (2023) argues that the youth in Northern Nigeria face immense pressures due to economic stagnation, leading some to perceive banditry as a viable option for survival. With limited access to formal employment, many young people seek alternatives, including illegal ventures, to meet their financial needs. The National Bureau of Statistics (2023) reports that youth unemployment rates in Northern Nigeria remain significantly higher than the national average, intensifying the appeal of criminal ventures for economic survival. Social disorganization theory offers additional insights by explaining how weakened community structures contribute to crime. Traditional networks of family and communal support have deteriorated under economic stress, leaving many young people isolated. It has been noted that “as family and communal bonds weaken under economic stress, criminal enterprises become a tempting alternative for survival” (Mohammed, 2023 p. 207). Cattle rustling and kidnaping for ransom, for example, provide quick financial rewards and have become common among some Fulani pastoralists in the Northwestern Nigeria. Displaced pastoralists, lacking education or economic alternatives, may become entangled in cycles of banditry.

Idleness, often criminalized as vagrancy, reflects societal attitudes towards non-work, with unstructured individuals often perceived as potential offenders (Barros, 2023). Structured leisure activities and engagement play a critical role in deterring delinquent behavior. Riley (1987) and Javier et al. (2013) highlight that teenagers' lifestyles, particularly their leisure activities, significantly correlate with delinquency, emphasizing the need for productive engagement. Similarly, Newton (2001) identifies boredom as a causal factor in youth criminality, particularly among males, reinforcing the importance of structured activities to mitigate negative behaviors.

Concerns that welfare schemes or basic income might promote idleness and crime are often based on assumptions rather than empirical data. Schroeder (2001) debunks this notion, explaining that fears about basic income leading to crime lack

² Previous literature that discuss the relationship between idleness and crimes include the works of Raphael & Winter-Ebmer (2001), Machin & Meghir (2004), Lin (2008), Fougère et al (2009), Jawadi et al (2021).

substantial evidence. Instead, constructive social interventions and meaningful engagement opportunities for youth are essential to reducing crime. Providing job training programs, employment opportunities, and skill development (especially in emerging sectors like technology and language services) can help Northwestern Nigerian youth find ethical means of living.

2.2 The Link Between Illiteracy and Crime

The connection between illiteracy and criminal activities is well-documented across various contexts, with studies indicating a strong correlation between low educational attainment and higher crime rates.³ Illiteracy limits access to legitimate employment opportunities and increases vulnerability to criminal activities, particularly in regions with economic instability. For instance, Hjalmarsson and Lochner (2012) found that 75% of state and 59% of federal inmates in the United States lacked a high school diploma, suggesting that education plays a crucial role in preventing delinquency.⁴

Education serves as a protective factor, providing individuals with the skills needed to participate in formal employment sectors and reducing their inclination toward illegal activities. Gong (2023) asserts that individuals with greater educational experience tend to display lower propensities for delinquency, as education broadens economic opportunities while fostering social and moral development. In regions like Northwestern Nigeria, however, where access to quality education remains limited, many young people find themselves excluded⁵ from these opportunities, increasing their susceptibility to criminal recruitment.

Moreover, poor literacy skills can act as a mediating factor in the development of criminal behavior. Briggs (2012) highlights that reading deficiencies not only impair cognitive development but also exacerbate feelings of frustration and social exclusion, which are often linked to delinquency. Without adequate educational support, many youths, especially those in rural or marginalized communities, lack the tools necessary to navigate societal expectations, making them more vulnerable to criminal networks.⁶

The consensus across multiple studies is that enhancing educational levels contributes to lower crime rates, as education offers a pathway to economic stability and personal growth (Crews, 2014; Pearman, 2014). This emphasizes the importance of implementing educational initiatives as a long-term strategy for crime prevention. In the context of Northwestern Nigeria, such initiatives must go beyond literacy programs and include vocational training that aligns with the local economy, offering practical alternatives to crime and fostering community resilience.

3.0 The Growing Banditry Crisis in Northwestern Nigeria

The rise of banditry in Northwestern Nigeria has evolved into a significant security and humanitarian crisis, destabilizing the region's social and economic foundations. This crisis (characterized by armed robberies, kidnappings for ransom, violent assaults on communities, and other minor criminal activities) has led to widespread displacement and severe disruptions to essential services, such as healthcare and education (Sani et al, 2022; Aina & Ojo, 2024). According to the International Crisis Group (2022), "Banditry has transformed from a localized issue to a nationwide crisis, with Northern Nigeria serving as a hotbed for these activities." Additionally, statistics from the Nigerian Police Force reveal that "in 2021 alone, over 1,400 people were kidnapped in the North, which is a clear indication of the growing influence of banditry" (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023).⁷

The humanitarian impact of banditry is devastating, with thousands displaced from their homes and entire communities left without access to basic services. Sani et al. (2024) report that disruptions to healthcare services in affected areas have contributed to rising malnutrition and increased mortality rates. Environmental degradation and loss of livelihoods, especially among displaced pastoralists, further exacerbate the crisis as noted by Amnesty International (2022). Similarly, Ejiofor (2024) has observed that this humanitarian fallout is compounded by the involvement of marginalized pastoralists, whose participation in banditry reflects unresolved socio-economic conflicts stemming from historical inequalities and exclusion.

³ Of the many previous studies that discuss the relationship between illiteracy and crime, there are: Gottfredson (1997), Harlow (2003), Crews & Montgomery (2001), Lochner & Moretti (2004), Tyler & Kling (2007), Ruddell & D'Arcy (2007), Snyder (2003), Vacca (2004), Wilson et al. (2000), and Muth & Walker (2013).

⁴ Although these figures are based on U.S. data, they reflect a global pattern that applies to many developing regions, including Northwestern Nigeria, where similar challenges are prevalent.

⁵ As noted by Sani et al. (2022) and Sarkin Gulbi (2024b), the actors often express concerns about being excluded from educational opportunities and other national benefits.

⁶ This is the case with some *mabarata* and Fulani pastoralists.

⁷ Unfortunately, interviews indicate that the number is most likely very much higher than this.

Socioeconomic challenges (such as high unemployment, poverty, and lack of education) play a great role in driving the banditry crisis. As the National Bureau of Statistics (2023 p. 11) highlights, “over 50% of the youth in Northwestern Nigeria are unemployed, with many lacking the necessary skills to compete in the job market.” In this context, banditry offers immediate financial rewards, making it a viable alternative to legitimate employment (Aiyede & Adetola, 2022). This is as Adebayo (2023 p. 128) adds “many young people see crime as their only viable option in the absence of meaningful employment.” Furthermore, the proliferation of drugs among bandits exacerbates the situation, as substance abuse has been identified as a critical catalyst for violent activities (Okoli & Aina, 2024).

Poor governance and ineffective law enforcement have also facilitated the growth of banditry. Many communities feel abandoned by the state, eroding trust in government institutions. As Adebayo (2023 p. 126) observes, “the ineffective response from security agencies has allowed bandits to operate with impunity, further encouraging criminal activities.” Corruption and underfunding of security forces hinder meaningful interventions, while some officers have been accused of collaborating with criminals (Usman & Zainab, 2022). This weak institutional response perpetuates the cycle of violence and creates an environment where crime can thrive.

Environmental factors, such as desertification and shrinking grazing lands, have also contributed to the crisis by displacing pastoralists, some of whom turn to banditry as a survival strategy. Without comprehensive interventions that address unemployment, weak governance, and social exclusion, the crisis is likely to persist, undermining regional stability (Olasupo et al., 2024). Confessions from the actors are often associated with issues such as corruption and the injustices perpetrated by Nigerian politicians. However, these confessions are always linked to factors like illiteracy and idleness.

4.0 Analyzing the Causes of Banditry in Northwestern Nigeria: Insights from Interview Respondents

Interviews conducted with various respondents provided critical insights into the underlying causes of banditry in Northwestern Nigeria. A recurring theme from the discussions was the alarming level of idleness and joblessness among the youth. Many of the respondents believe that “unemployment is a pressing concern, and without job opportunities, young men often find themselves lured into banditry as a means of survival.” This sentiment is linked to a broader issue in the region, where economic instability has left many young individuals feeling hopeless and desperate, leading them to criminal activities as a seemingly viable alternative. Similarly, K. Sani (personal communication, 25th September 2024) noted that “many youths are frustrated with their lack of prospects, pushing them towards crime for quick financial gains.” In Nigeria generally, “the unemployment rate stood at 5.3 percent in the first quarter of 2024, representing a third consecutive increase since the second quarter of 2023” (Nigerian Economic Submit Group, 2024 para. 2).

Fig. 1: Nigeria’s Unemployment Rate in 2024 Q1

Source: Nigerian Economic Submit Group (2024)

One of the critical issues contributing to banditry in Northwestern Nigeria is the high number of out-of-school children, particularly among the *mabarata* population and Fulani pastoralists. Several respondents highlighted the alarming rate of educational deprivation among these groups. A.R. Dangulbi (personal communication, 25th August 2024) remarked, “The *Almajiri* system⁸ has failed many children; they are sent to cities in the name of religious education but end of *begging* and receive no formal schooling or vocational skills.” The *maba* (begging) and pastoralism saga represent a significant challenge, as they have perpetuated cycles of poverty and criminality.⁹

Moreover, the situation for many Fulani youths engaged in herding is similarly dire. Many of them are uneducated and lack vocational skills, which leaves them susceptible to conflicts over land and resources with settled communities. H.U. Maikwari (personal communication, 9th September 2024) emphasized that “the traditional lifestyle of the Fulani can lead to escalations in violence and banditry, particularly when economic opportunities are scarce.” This view is in line with the position of International Crisis Group (2022), which reported that “the rising tide of cattle rustling among Fulani youths is exacerbated by economic disenfranchisement and the lack of alternative livelihoods.” The respondents consistently indicated that these conflicts often spiral into criminal activities, as frustrated youths resort to banditry as a means of survival.

The interviews revealed a consensus that the absence of educational and vocational training severely limits the options available to out-of-school children, particularly in the *almajiri* and Fulani communities. Many respondents highlighted the critical role of education in combating banditry. A.M. Umar (personal communication, September 2024) stated, “Illiteracy is a significant factor in the recruitment of youth into banditry. When children lack formal education, they have few alternatives.”

It has been especially stressed that “To break the cycle of poverty and criminality, we must integrate these children into formal educational systems.” This sentiment was echoed by several respondents, who advocated for inclusive educational policies that provide not only academic knowledge but also practical skills. Incorporating vocational skills into the curriculum can provide both *almajiri* and Fulani children with pathways to legitimate employment. There are needs to create programs that cater to the unique needs of these children, combining religious education with vocational training.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The rise of banditry in Northwestern Nigeria is deeply complex with critical factors affecting the youth, particularly idleness and illiteracy. A significant proportion of young individuals in the region lack access to quality education, rendering them ill-equipped to secure legitimate employment. This lack of educational opportunities leads to pervasive idleness, with many young men feeling trapped in a cycle of hopelessness. As a result, frustration over their unemployment often pushes them toward criminal activities, as they perceive banditry as a viable means of survival. The relationship between idleness and criminal behavior is stark.

In addition to the challenges of illiteracy and idleness, issues specific to the Fulani population further complicate the saga of banditry. Many Fulani youths engaged in herding lack formal education and vocational skills, which restricts their economic opportunities. Their traditional lifestyle often leads to conflicts with settled communities over land and resources, which can escalate into criminal activities, including cattle rustling and banditry. Economic disenfranchisement and the absence of alternative livelihoods have exacerbated these tensions, making it essential to address the specific needs and grievances of the Fulani population to mitigate their susceptibility to involvement in criminal activities.

The *bara* saga presents another layer of complexity in the discourse on banditry in the Northwestern Nigeria. The absence of structured support for these *mabarata* and out-of-school children renders them vulnerable to exploitation by criminal groups. Unfortunately, the ongoing cycle of banditry has resulted in increased displacement of villagers. This, in turn, leads to higher levels of illiteracy and idleness, pushing children toward following unethical means of survival.

5.2 Recommendations

To effectively tackle the issues highlighted in the findings, a comprehensive strategy is necessary. Firstly, investment in vocational training programs must be prioritized. The government should allocate resources to establish vocational training centers focusing on skills relevant to the local economy, such as agriculture, technology, and craftsmanship.

⁸ The *Almajiri* system, originally designed to provide religious education, has devolved into a situation where many children are left to fend for themselves without adequate support. As noted by many respondents, the absence of structured support leaves many *mabarata* and out-of-school children vulnerable to exploitation by criminal groups who prey on their desperation. This highlights the relationship between idleness, illiteracy and crime.

⁹ It is believed that without education, these children (limited to begging and pastoralism) often find themselves without options, making them easy targets for criminal organizations.

Such initiatives can significantly enhance employability and provide alternative income pathways for vulnerable youth, ultimately reducing the prevalence of idleness and the allure of criminal activities. The activities of such establishments must be consistently monitored to ensure that no element of corruption exists.

Next, addressing the specific needs of the Fulani population is crucial. Targeted interventions should aim to provide educational opportunities and vocational training for Fulani youths, specifically the pastoralists. These programs could help them acquire essential skills, thus improving their economic prospects and reducing their vulnerability to criminal recruitment. Additionally, conflict resolution strategies that promote dialogue between settled communities and Fulani herders can help mitigate land disputes and foster more harmonious relations.

Lastly, reforms are needed to improve the *almajiri* system by integrating it into formal education and vocational training and reducing *bara* practices. This can involve developing a curriculum that combines religious education with practical skills, ensuring that *almajiri* children are equipped for future employment opportunities. Providing structured support and mentorship can empower these children, steering them away from paths leading to criminality. Northwestern Nigeria can break the cycle of poverty and banditry, ultimately leading to a more stable and prosperous future, by fostering an environment that values education and skills development.

5.3 Conclusion

Addressing banditry in Northwestern Nigeria necessitates a comprehensive strategy that considers employment, education, and community engagement. The research highlights that the rise of banditry and crime are systematically linked to high unemployment rates, lack of educational opportunities, and socioeconomic disenfranchisement among the youth. Stakeholders can empower young individuals, creating pathways for legitimate employment and reducing the appeal of crime by investing in the development of vocational training programs and integrating educational systems. Furthermore, fostering community involvement and collaborative efforts between government and private sectors will help cultivate a more stable and secure environment. Ultimately, Northwestern Nigeria can work towards a prosperous and crime-free future by truthfully tackling the root causes of banditry and fostering a sense of belonging and purpose among the youth.

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